

Effect of Adverse Childhood Experiences on the Mental Health of Adults

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Abstract

Background: Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) are traumatic incidents before the age of 18 years that can lead to health problems. Globally, it is estimated that 40 million children suffer from abuse or neglect. ACEs have long-term effects on physical and mental health. There is a lack of research on the prevalence of ACEs in Saudi Arabia. Moreover, information is scarce regarding the correlation between ACEs and the mental health of adults. This study was conducted to assess the impact of ACEs on mental health (social anxiety disorder (SAD), aggression, and low self-esteem) among adults in the Middle Region of Saudi Arabia.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 430 adults. An online self-administered questionnaire was used, and it included five sections, which are sociodemographic characteristics, assessment of ACEs, aggression, SAD, and self-esteem.

Results: The prevalence of ACEs was high, with 48% of participants reporting having five or more ACEs. There was a significant association between ACEs and aggression. Those with a high level of aggression had a higher score of ACEs compared to those with low aggression levels (6.3 ± 2.6 Vs. 3.2 ± 2.2). This difference was statistically highly significant ($F= 26.7$ and $p < .0001$). Participants with a high level of SAD had a higher score of ACEs compared to those with low SAD levels (5.5 ± 2.5 Vs. 3.9 ± 2.5). This difference was statistically highly significant ($F= 21.7$ and $p < .0001$). Those with a low level of self-esteem had a higher score of ACEs compared to those with high

More Information

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Adverse childhood experiences, aggression, social anxiety disorder, self-esteem.

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self-esteem levels (6.6 ± 1.8 Vs 3.4 ± 2.3). This difference was statistically highly significant ($F= 29.3$ and $p <.0001$). Conclusions: There is a high prevalence of ACEs among adults. ACEs were significantly linked to low self-esteem, aggression, and SAD in adulthood. Sexual abuse and physical neglect were identified as common predictors of these mental health issues. It is recommended that other studies to be conducted to explore the key factors contributing to the high prevalence of ACEs and to understand the impact of ACEs on the physical health of adults as well.

Introduction

Background

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) encompass a variety of traumatic incidents that occur before a person reaches 18 years of age, causing harm and potentially leading to lasting health and well-being issues [1]. Examples of ACEs include different forms of abuse (physical, sexual, emotional, and peer sexual abuse), neglect (psychological and physical neglect), and household dysfunction (such as parental divorce, or domestic violence) [1]. Globally, it is estimated that 40 million children suffer from abuse or neglect, and research indicates that a significant portion of women and men have experienced sexual abuse during childhood [2]. Additionally, the World Health Organization reports that a large proportion of young children between the ages of 2-4 years regularly face physical punishment or psychological violence from parents or caregivers [2]. People do not realize that exposure to ACEs is linked to increased health risks throughout life [3]. In the United States, around 64% of American adults have disclosed experiencing at least one Adverse Childhood Experience (ACE) before reaching the age of eighteen, and approximately 1 in 6 (17.3%) have reported encountering four or more ACEs [3]. Similarly, studies conducted in Serbia revealed that roughly 70 out of every 100 adults have suffered from at least one form of ACE during their childhood and around 20 individuals have reported experiencing four or more ACEs [1]. In Bermuda, Canada, and the United States the burden of ACE related to health risks is estimated at \$748 billion annually [3]. In Saudi Arabia, the prevalence of ACEs is notably high, with 87.7% of participants indicating they have encountered at least one ACE, and 49.2% have reported experiencing four or more. [4].

It is crucial to emphasize that children are innocent victims and should never be held responsible for instances of abuse [2]. Certain characteristics of a child may increase the likelihood of maltreatment, such as being under the age of four or being an adolescent, being unwanted or not living up to parental expectations, having special needs, crying persistently, having unusual physical features, or having an intellectual or neurological disorder [2].

Parental or caregiver characteristics that may raise the risk of child maltreatment include trouble bonding with a baby, not nurturing the child, having been maltreated as a child, lacking information about child development, having unrealistic expectations, misusing

alcohol or drugs (even during pregnancy), having low self-esteem, suffering from poor impulse control or having a neurological or mental illness, engaging in criminal activity, or having financial issues [2].

Other factors that may increase the risk of child maltreatment include the following: a lack of support system, social isolation, violence amongst family members, and a breakdown in the family's ability to support the child-rearing process [2].

Exposure to ACEs can have a significant and long-lasting impact on an individual's health and well-being. Children with higher ACE scores are more likely to experience: Physical health problems: including an increased risk of heart disease, stroke, diabetes, poor sleep, cancer, and increased risk of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs), and injury [5] Although, the majority of earlier research on ACEs was conducted in high-income countries [5]. It is uncertain if these findings apply to low- and middle-income nations, where ACEs are more common [5]. In China, at least one ACE was common among individuals, which is consistent with prior studies [5].

The study also found that the more ACEs a person has faced, the greater their probability of adopting risky behaviors and morbidity in adulthood [5]. Physical abuse has been connected to chronic illness, poor mental health, and smoking [5]. Emotional abuse during childhood was found to be associated with a higher risk of depression and PTSD in adulthood [5]. Abuse and neglect can cause emotional dysregulation and an increase in cortisol levels, which can affect the metabolic, cardiovascular, immune, and neurological systems [5].

These potentially negative consequences are mostly caused by physiological responses to psychosocial stress, such as toxic stress, which can build up and interact over time, social and emotional problems: like increasing the likelihood of criminal involvement, they also hurt an individual's academic performance, and decrease the likelihood of being productive members of society [5].

Most studies on Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) have focused on children rather than adults, and there is a lack of research on the prevalence of ACEs in the Middle Region of Saudi Arabia. Additionally, studies in Saudi Arabia have been the correlation between ACEs and physical health in adults, without considering their impact on mental health such as self-esteem, aggression, and social disorders.

Aim of Study

Assess the impact of ACE on mental health (Social anxiety disorder, Aggression, low self-esteem) among adults in the Middle Region of Saudi Arabia.

Methods**Study Design**

A cross-sectional study.

Study Setting

Saudi Arabia.

Study Population

Adults living in the middle region of Saudi Arabia.

Inclusion Criteria

Adults aged 18 years or more of both genders and living in the middle. region.

Exclusion Criteria

Those aged 65 and over were excluded.

Study Duration

Data collection was between January and February 2024.

Sampling method

The sample size was calculated by using n4Studies software. The study population is more than 10,000[6]. So the sample was calculated using a 95% confidence interval, 0.5 proportion, 0.05 degree of accuracy, and 80% power of the study. The calculated sample from the equation: $n = Z^2pq/d^2$ was 385. According to the Saudi General Authority of Statistics, the adult population aged 20-64 in the middle region (Riyadh and al-Qassim) was 6,830,778 million people. The total number of participants included in the study was 430.

Sampling Technique

The questionnaire was designed and conducted online using the non-probability, convenient sampling technique. The questionnaire link was distributed via social media such as X and WhatsApp.

The Research Instrument

An online questionnaire was used, and it was composed of five sections, which are sociodemographic characteristics, assessment of ACE, aggression, SAD, and self-esteem.

Section 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics

Consisted of 8 questions that covered the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants such as gender, age, education level, and income.

Section 2: ACEs

ACEs were evaluated using the Adverse Childhood Experiences International Questionnaire (ACE-IQ), which is a validated screening instrument that was developed by the World Health Organization to measure ACEs in all countries [7]. ACE-IQ is designed for administration to people aged 18 years and older. In our study, we modified the ACE-IQ to assess exposure to 11 types of ACEs, including emotional abuse, physical abuse, sexual abuse, violence against household members, living with household members who were mentally ill or suicidal or imprisoned, having one or no

parents, parental separation or divorce, emotional neglect, physical neglect, and bullying. Some variables were assessed with 4 responses, namely (many times (3 or more), few times (once or twice), once, and never). However, other variables such as living with household members who were mentally ill or imprisoned, having one or no parents, and experiencing parental separation or divorce were assessed as either (yes or no). To calculate the total events of the Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs), variables were recoded into a binary level, where "0" represented (no or never) and "1" represented (yes or once or more). For the emotional neglect category (Did the parents or guardians understand your problems and worries?) that included two responses, the score was reversed. A respondent was given "1" if they answered "no" and "0" if they answered, "yes". The total score of ACEs was calculated. It represents the types of ACEs that were experienced by the individual. ACEs were categorized into five categories: no ACE, at least one form of ACE, two to four forms of ACE, five to seven forms of ACE, and eight or more forms of ACE.

Section 3: Self-esteem

We modified the scale for self-esteem. Developed by Morris Rosenberg [8]. The Rosenberg Self-Esteem (RSE) scale is designed to assess self-esteem. It includes 12 statements such as (I feel I do not have much to be proud of, I certainly feel useless, and I wish I could have more respect for myself). It was assessed by a 5-point Likert scale with 1= strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree. The maximum score that can be achieved was 60, while the minimum score was 12. Participants were categorized into three categories: scores higher than 44 were considered to have high self-esteem, scores in the range of 28 to 44 were considered as moderate self-esteem, and scores lower than 28 were considered to have low self-esteem.

Section 4: SAD

The Severity Measure for Social Anxiety Disorder for Adults was used to assess the severity of Social Anxiety Disorder in the participants [9]. The 10 questions cover the past seven days and include (felt moments of sudden terror, fear, or fright in social situations, avoided, or did not approach or enter, social situations, and left social situations early or participating only minimally). The questions were rated on a (0=Never; 1=Occasionally; 2=Half of the time; 3=Most of the time; and 4=All of the time). The range of total scores for social anxiety disorder is from 0 to 40, where higher scores indicate more social anxiety disorder. They were categorized into high SAD 27 and more, moderate SAD 14 to 26, and no SAD from 0 to 13.

Section 5: Aggression

The assessment of aggression consisted of 12 statements, which were measured using a modified scale [10] It included 7 statements to assess physical

aggression such as the following: (Once in a while, I can't control the urge to strike another person, I have threatened people I know). And 5 statements to measure verbal Aggression such as the following: (I often find myself disagreeing with people, when people annoy me, I may tell them what I think of them, my friends say that I'm somewhat argumentative). This section was assessed using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from (strongly agree:5 agree:4 neutral :3 disagree:2 Strongly disagree:1). The total aggression score was calculated, and the responses to all 12 questions were summed up. The maximum score that can be achieved was 60, while the minimum score was 12. Participants were categorized into high aggression, moderate aggression, and low aggression based on their scores. Scores higher than 44 were considered as high aggression, scores in the range of 28 to 44 were considered as moderate aggression, and scores lower than 28 were considered as low aggression.

Validity and Reliability of the Questionnaires

Validity

Cross-translation: For all used questionnaires, a cross-translation was done by translating the original English version of the questionnaire into Arabic. The Arabic translation was then sent to an independent translator, who translated it back into English. The translated English version was then compared to the original English version to ensure the accuracy of the translation.

Face validity: The 5 questionnaires underwent revisions based on feedback from an expert in clinical psychology from Princess Nourah University.

Validity was tested statistically for each questionnaire separately. All questions in all questionnaires were highly positively correlated with the overall total scores, r was more than 0.3 for all questions, and p-values were all less than 0.05.

Reliability

The reliability of each questionnaire employed in this study was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, calculated with JMP statistical software. For the AECs questionnaire, α was 0.79, and for the aggression questionnaire, α was 0.80. Social anxiety disorder questionnaire, α was 0.9, and for the self-esteem questionnaire, α was 0.82.

Statistical Analysis

John's Macintosh Project (JMP) version 17 was used for statistical analysis [11]. Descriptive statistics of demographic variables, such as gender, age, educational level, occupational status, and marital status, were presented in frequency tables. To compare means, ANOVA/ and t-tests were used. Multiple linear regression models were used to investigate the prediction of the three mental health conditions using different types of ACEs. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1 demonstrates the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants. Almost half of the participants' ages ranged around 22–45 (46.98%), and (78.37%) of the participants were female, and 59.77% of the participants were single. The majority of the population had a college/university degree (70.47%), and (1.63%) of the participants had a primary/secondary/school certificate. Regarding the parent's education level, the most prevalent educational level was college/university (31.16% and 29.77%, respectively). More than half (66.51%) of the participants are not working. and half of the participants had enough income (58.84%). The prevalence of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) in the studied sample was investigated. About half of the studied sample (48%) experienced 5 or more forms of ACEs, while only 6.05% of the participants never experienced any form of ACEs.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Studied Sample (n = 430)

		N	%
Age	18 -21	176	40.93%
	22-45	202	46.98%
	46-60	49	11.40%
	More than 60	3	0.70%
Sex	Male	93	21.63%
	Female	337	78.37%
Marital Status	Single	257	59.77%
	Married	159	36.98%
	Divorced	13	3.02%
	Widowed	1	0.23%
Level of education	primary /Secondary school completed.	7	1.63%
	The high school completed.	87	20.23%
	College/Unaiversity completed.	303	70.47%
	Postgraduate degree.	33	7.67%

Father's education	Primary / Secondary school completed.	96	22.33%
	The high school completed.	105	24.42%
	College/University completed.	134	31.16%
	Postgraduate degree.	47	10.93%
	Not education.	48	11.16%
Mother's education	Primary / Secondary school completed.	104	24.19%
	The high school completed.	85	19.77%
	College/University completed.	128	29.77%
	Postgraduate degree.	20	4.65%
	Not education.	93	21.63%
Job	Working.	144	33.49%
	Not Working.	286	66.51%
Income	Not enough	95	22.09%
	Enough	253	58.84%
	Enough and spared	82	19.07%

Table 2 shows the prevalence of different types of ACE among the participants. Those who were exposed to household violence were more than half of the sample, representing 56.74%. While experiencing physical neglect was reported in about one-quarter of the sample. Those who were ever exposed to community violence were the majority of the sample (77.67%). It was also found that those who were exposed to bullying constituted 60.47%. As for the types of abuse during childhood, half of the participants (50.23%) experienced physical abuse at least once in their lives, and slightly more than half of them (62.79%) experienced emotional abuse. Participants who experienced sexual abuse were 27.21%. Only 7.67% of

the participants experienced living with an incarcerated person. And 19.30% of the participants lived with a person with a mental illness. Also, 11.16% experienced living with divorced parents. Those who suffered from emotional neglect at least once in their life were 50.70%.

The prevalence of each mental status Self-esteem, SAD, and aggression was studied. The majority of the population had moderate to high self-esteem levels (96%), and only 3.72% had a low level of self-esteem. As regard SAD, about one-third of the sample had a moderate to high degree of SAD (32.7%). While 70% of the sample had a moderate to high aggression level.

Table 2: Prevalence of Different Types of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) in the Sample (n = 430)

Type of ACE	N	% of Total
Physical abuse		
No	214	49.77%
Yes	216	50.23%
Emotional abuse		
No	160	37.21%
Yes	270	62.79%
Sexual abuse		
No	313	72.79%
Yes	117	27.21%
Incarcerated household		
No	397	92.33%
Yes	33	7.67%
Household with mental illness		
No	347	80.70%
Yes	83	19.30%
Divorced parents		
No	382	88.84%
Yes	48	11.16%
Emotional neglect		
No	218	50.70%
Yes	212	49.30%

Household violence		
No	186	43.26%
Yes	244	56.74%
Physical neglect		
No	334	77.67%
Yes	96	22.33%
Bullying		
No	170	39.53%
Yes	260	60.47%
Community violence		
No	96	22.33%
Yes	334	77.67%

Table 3 demonstrates the impact of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) on the mental health of adults in the study, including aggression, social anxiety disorder (SAD), and self-esteem. All these factors were significantly associated with adverse childhood experiences (ACEs). The table shows that those with a low level of self-esteem had a higher score of ACEs compared to those with high self-esteem levels (6.6±1.8 Vs 3.4±2.3). This difference was statistically

highly significant (F= 29.3 and p= <.0001). Participants with a high level of SAD had a higher score of ACEs compared to those with low SAD levels (5.5±2.5 vs. 3.9±2.5). This difference was statistically highly significant (F= 21.68 and p= <.0001). Those with a high level of aggression had a higher score of ACEs compared to those with low aggression levels (6.3 ±2.6 Vs. 3.2 ± 2.2). This difference was statistically highly significant (F= 26.7 and p= <.0001).

Table 3: Impact of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) on the Mental Health of Adults

Factors	Score of ACEs	Test of significance
	X ±SD	
Self-esteem		ANOVA
High Self-esteem level	3.4 ± 2.4	F= 29.3
Moderate Self-esteem level	5.1 ± 2.5	p= <.0001*
Low Self-esteem level	6.6 ± 1.8	
Social anxiety disorder (SAD)		ANOVA
High SAD level	5.5 ± 2.5	F= 21.7
Moderate SAD level	5.6 ± 2.5	p= <.0001*
Low SAD level	3.9 ± 2.5	
Aggression		ANOVA
High aggression level	6.3 ± 2.6	F= 26.7
Moderate aggression level	4.8 ± 2.6	p= <.0001*
Low aggression level	3.3 ± 2.2	

Note: *p<0.05

Table 4 shows A multiple linear regression predicting self-esteem levels based on ACE categories. The regression equation was significant (F= 27.1925 p=<.0001, with an R square of 0.196283). The

significant predictors of self-esteem were (in descending order): emotional neglect followed by sexual abuse, physical neglect, and lastly emotional abuse.

Table 4: Regression Model Predicting Self-Esteem Based on Different Types of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE)

Term	Estimate	Std Error	t Ratio	Prob> t
Intercept	45.905471	0.569439	80.62	<.0001*
emotional abuse (yes, no)	-2.572758	0.692172	-3.72	0.0002*
sexual abuse (yes, no)	-2.852034	0.738922	-3.86	0.0001*
emotional neglect (yes, no)	-3.205144	0.641494	-5.00	<.0001*
physical neglect (yes, no)	-2.721856	0.776967	-3.50	0.0005*

Note: *p<0.05

Table. 5 shows A multiple linear regression predicting social anxiety disorder (SAD) levels based on ACE categories. The regression equation was significant (F= 18.2018, P<.0001, with an R square of 0.138221). The

significant predictors of SAD were (in descending order): household violence followed by emotional neglect, physical neglect, and lastly, sexual abuse.

Table 5: Regression Model Predicting Social Anxiety Disorder Based on Different Types of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE)

Term	Estimate	Std Error	t Ratio	Prob> t
Intercept	6.5830966	0.6451	10.20	<.0001*
sexual abuse (yes, no)	1.8233126	0.88848	2.05	0.0408*
emotional neglect (yes, no)	2.8955468	0.779353	3.72	0.0002*
household violence (yes, no)	3.2534162	0.822836	3.95	<.0001*
physical neglect (yes, no)	2.6862304	0.929599	2.89	0.0041*

Note: *p<0.05

Table. 6 shows multiple linear regression predicting aggression based on ACE types. The regression equation was significant (F= 24.04208, p<.0001, with an R square of 0.176849). The significant predictors of

aggression were (in descending order): physical neglect followed by physical abuse and sexual abuse, and lastly, community violence.

Table 6: Regression Model Predicting Aggression Based on Different Types of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE)

Term	Estimate	Std Error	t Ratio	Prob> t
Intercept	27.336733	0.792572	34.49	<.0001*
physical abuse (yes, no)	2.9397552	0.794555	3.70	0.0002*
sexual abuse (yes, no)	2.2766556	0.886264	2.57	0.0105*
physical neglect (yes, no)	4.8509591	0.901464	5.38	<.0001*
community violence (yes, no)	2.1292128	0.923548	2.31	0.0216*

Note: *p<0.05

Discussion

The study aimed to assess the prevalence of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) and their impact on mental health outcomes, including social anxiety disorder (SAD), aggression, and low self-esteem, among adults in the middle region of Saudi Arabia. The results of this research revealed a high prevalence of ACEs, with 48% of participants reporting having five or more ACEs and 10% having one form of ACE. Evidence from a retrospective cohort study conducted in 2020 in the Eastern region of KSA on the rate of ACEs was high among adults, with 81% exposed to four or more forms of ACEs, which is consistent with the results of the current study [12]. Another study was conducted in Egypt about mothers, 66% of whom were exposed to at least one ACE [13]. The incidence of ACEs was high globally as well, with the CDC indicating that about 64% of adults in the United States were exposed to at least one type of ACE, and 17.3% of adults were exposed to four or more types of ACEs [3]. The current study showed that the most common ACEs were community violence (77.67%), followed by emotional abuse (62.79%), and bullying (60.47%). Consistent with the present study, another study conducted in KSA reported that most cases of ACEs were emotional neglect (82.2%), followed by community violence

(76.3%), and witnessing family members being treated violently (74%) [12].

Community violence was high in both studies. This may be due to societal standards that accept strict upbringing methods as a positive disciplinary practice, whether in the family or school. This may be also attributed to a lack of awareness that the spread of domestic violence may lead to community violence. These results indicate that the overall prevalence of ACEs is consistently high globally.

As regards the effect of ACEs on self-esteem in adulthood, the current study showed that there is a significant relationship between adverse childhood experiences and low self-esteem in adulthood, as it was found that the higher the exposure to ACEs, the lower the rate of self-esteem. This could be explained by the fact that the child who had an adverse childhood experience will continue to feel inferior in his life thereafter. The influence of ACEs that comes at a young age is usually difficult to change unless effort is made, and the person is prepared to make a change. The present study also investigated which types of ACEs were linked to low self-esteem and these types are emotional neglect, sexual abuse, physical abuse, and emotional abuse. When a child is neglected by his parents regarding his problems and fears, he may start

feeling that no one else can understand him and he may feel unappreciated. The extent to which the parents understand their child's problems and fears makes the child feel how important he is and how important his feelings are [14].

The Child Welfare Information Gateway reported slightly different results. It reported that there was a negative correlation between self-esteem and all forms of ACEs except sexual abuse and community violence. [15]. However, the sample of this study was only males, and this study was conducted in Tehran, the capital of Iran. This may lead to an underestimation of the real sexual abuse issue from the collected data due to the preservative culture in this country [14].

The current study showed a significant association between social anxiety disorders and negative childhood experiences (ACE) among adults. About one-third of the sample had a moderate to high degree of SAD. Also, the occurrence of social anxiety is affected by some types of ACEs, where the results showed that the most common predictor is domestic violence, followed by emotional neglect, physical neglect, and, finally, sexual abuse. These traumatic events might interfere with the growth of emotional wellness, which can later in life make it challenging for people to handle social circumstances. These findings were supported by a study conducted by Duygu Yücel *et al* in Turkey (2024). That study indicated a significant positive relationship between ACEs and SAD symptoms in adulthood [16]. Higher ACE experience was associated with an increased likelihood of social anxiety symptoms [16].

This study also found a significant association between aggression and adverse childhood experiences (ACE). This association can be explained by the fact that children who have been exposed to abuse, neglect, or violence are more likely to become aggressive themselves and are more susceptible to be involved in delinquency and crime later in life [15].

A study conducted in California found similar findings; an increase in ACEs was associated with an increase in aggression in women, with physical aggression notably higher than verbal aggression [17]. On the other hand, McRae *et al* (2021) found that ACE exposure in childhood does not influence aggression [18]. This could be due to the difference in the age group in the sample of that study as the participants were children and early adolescents (6–14 years), while the sample in the present study included only adults older than 18, which the impact of ACEs could be clearer than in children. In the present study, it was found that some forms of ACEs were significant predictors of aggression; these were physical neglect, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and community violence.

Individuals who have experienced physical neglect and sexual abuse may experience intense emotions such as

anger and frustration, which can lead to aggression. These feelings often arise from shame and inadequacy, significantly impacting their ability to trust others. The resulting lack of trust can make social interactions very stressful and anxiety-inducing, and it may be challenging for them to develop a healthy sense of self-esteem. Future studies could investigate why sexual abuse and physical neglect are predictors of three mental conditions: self-esteem, aggression, and SAD.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the present study revealed a high prevalence of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) among the participants, with about half of them experiencing five or more ACEs. ACEs were significantly linked to low self-esteem, aggression, and social anxiety disorder (SAD) during adulthood. Specific types of ACEs, notably sexual abuse and physical neglect, were identified as common predictors of the three mental health conditions (low self-esteem, SAD, and aggression), highlighting the pervasive impact of ACEs on adult mental well-being.

Strengths and Limitations

Strengths such as high statistical power of the study as the sample was even more than the calculated size and the good representation of the study population as regards different sociodemographic criteria in the studied participants.

Limitations of the convenient sampling technique that was used. Some individuals with mental disorders may not be willing to talk about them voluntarily.

Recommendation

Further studies are needed to investigate in depth the leading factors of ACE in Saudi society. Studies are needed to investigate the potential impact of ACEs on physical health as well. Creating interventions to improve mental health, identifying protective factors to prevent the negative effects of ACEs, and providing adequate mental health resources should be essential steps in mitigating the long-term effects of childhood adversity. The role of health education should be added to promote mental health and prevent the worsening of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs). This can be achieved by empowering health educators in schools and organizing awareness campaigns to educate society and families and eliminate the stigma associated with mental health.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Meaning
ACEs	Adverse Childhood Experiences
US	United States
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
PTSD	post-traumatic stress disorder
SAD	Social anxiety disorder
ACE-IQ	Adverse Childhood Experiences International Questionnaire

RSE	Rosenberg Self-Esteem
JMP	John's Macintosh Project
KSA	Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
PNU	Princess Nourah University
IRB	Institutional review board

Availability of Data and Materials

The datasets used are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Authors' Contributions

All authors contributed to the study substantially and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

The participants' informed consent was taken before they fill in the questionnaire; they were informed of the study's purpose with the right to withdraw anytime. They were assured that the data will be used only for research purposes and all the information will be kept, confidential and anonymous. IRB approval was taken from the PNU institutional review board before the distribution of the questionnaire; log number: 23-1020.

Consent for Publication

Not applicable.

Competing Interests

The authors have no potential conflict of interest disclosed.

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